

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)

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Abstract—Complex machine learning models perform better. However, we consider these models as black boxes. That’s where Explainable AI (XAI) comes into play. Understanding why a model makes a specific prediction can be as crucial as its accuracy for many applications, researchers, and decision-makers. In many real-world applications, the explainability and transparency of AI systems are indispensable. The research community and industry are giving growing attention to explainability and explainable AI. Compared to traditional machine learning methods, deep neural networks (DNNs) have been very successful. DNNs are comparably weak in explaining their inference processes and results because the data input passes through many layers, and a single prediction can involve millions of mathematical operations. It is difficult for humans to follow the exact mapping from data input to the predicted result. We would have to consider millions of weights that interact in a complex way to understand a prediction by a neural network. To interpret the behavior and predictions of neural networks, we need specific interpretation methods. Thus, a new frontier is opening for researchers.

Index Terms—Explainable, Explainability, Interpretability, Artificial Intelligence, Machine learning, Deep learning, Survey

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite widespread adoption, machine learning models remain mostly black boxes. Nobody likes a black-box model. We can build good models with sophisticated algorithms and a fair amount of data preparation. However, can we explain what’s going on internally? That’s where Explainable AI (XAI) comes into play. Knowing why the model makes predictions the way it does is essential for tweaking. Understanding why a model makes a specific prediction can be as crucial as its accuracy for many applications. It is critical in assessing the trust of a model. Trustworthiness is fundamental if one plans to act based on a model prediction and decides whether to deploy a new model. Such understanding also provides insights into the model, which we can use to transform an untrustworthy model or prediction into a trustworthy one.

In machine learning, model complexity is directly proportional to model performance. Complex machine learning

models like the deep learning model perform better than interpretable models like the linear regression model. We achieve the highest accuracy for large modern datasets by complex models that even experts struggle to interpret, such as an ensemble of deep learning models, creating a tension between accuracy and interpretability. Introducing explainability is proved challenging as it is inverse to its prediction accuracy. Thus, it translates into a trade-off between accuracy and interpretability.

In many real-world applications, the explainability and transparency of AI systems are indispensable. The research community and industry are giving growing attention to explainability and explainable AI. The explainability is essential for their users, the affected people by AI decisions, and the researchers and developers who create the AI solutions. Hence to reinforce our motivation, we need model interpretation such that we can account for fairness (unbiasedness/non-discriminative), accountability (reliable results), and transparency (being able to query and validate predictive decisions) of a predictive model. We will look further into the state-of-the-art techniques and the future for explainable deep learning.

II. TRADITIONAL TECHNIQUES FOR MODEL INTERPRETATION

For a long time, we considered looking into features as model Interpretation. Dimensionality reduction algorithms like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) help us find the most influential features from a substantial feature space. On the other hand, clustering algorithms like Hierarchical Clustering also help find input features related to each other. These techniques assist us to understand more about our data, features, and models that might be effective. However, they are somewhat limiting in terms of trying to discern human-interpretable ways of how a model works. In the real world, a model’s performance often decreases and plateaus over time after deployment. Hence simply re-training a model on the same

feature set will not be sufficient, and we need to constantly check for how important input features are in deciding model predictions and how well they might be working on new data points. A better interpretation may be needed to identify the blind spots in the algorithms to build a secure and safe model by fixing the training data set prone to adversarial attacks.

A. Using Interpretable Models

The easiest way to get started with model interpretation is to use interpretable models out of the box! The interpretable models typically include regular parametric models like linear regression, logistic regression, tree-based models, rule-fits, and even models like k-nearest neighbors and Naive Bayes! All of these are Rule-based AI, and these are easy for humans to understand and interpret. However, we must understand that some of these models might be too simplistic, and hence we might need to think of better ways to build and interpret more complex and better performing models.

B. Identifying Important Features

Feature importance is a generic term for explaining the degree to which a predictive model relies on a particular feature. The first technique for explaining what machine learning models are doing is Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations [7] (LIME). LIME supports explanations for tabular models, text classifiers, and image classifiers. It has got some criticism on lack of stability, consistency (changing the model does not decrease the attribution of a variable if its contribution increases or remains the same), and missingness

SHapley Additive exPlanations [3] (SHAP) is a game-theoretic approach to explaining the output of any machine learning model. It connects optimal credit allocation (feature contributions) with local explanations using the classic Shapley values from game theory and their related extensions. LIME works better to grasp a single prediction and explain it. SHAP works better for the entire model (or single variable) explanation. We use SHAP for summary plots and dependence plots.

The authors [6] explore explainability methods in the domain of real-time fraud detection. They used multiple datasets for the case study, evaluated multiple ML models, used traditional logistic regression to identify top-10 global features of the dataset. They also applied LIME and SHAP to identify top-10 global features for each ML model and reported the runtime for single-instance explanation (in seconds). It proves that Explainable AI can successfully indicate data or concept drift of the model.

III. TOWARDS COMPLEX MODELS

Deep Learning has made a significant contribution to the recent progress in artificial intelligence (AI). Compared to traditional machine learning methods, Deep learning has been very successful, especially in tasks that involve images and texts, such as image classification and language translation. The success story of deep neural networks began in 2012 when

a deep learning approach won the ImageNet image classification challenge. Since then, we have witnessed an explosion of deep neural network architectures, with a trend towards deeper networks with more and more weight parameters.

However, deep neural networks (DNNs) are comparably weak in explaining their inference processes and results, and they are typically treated as a black box by both developers and users. To make predictions with a neural network, the data input is passed through many layers of multiplication with the learned weights and through non-linear transformations. A single prediction can involve millions of mathematical operations depending on the architecture of the neural network. There is no chance that we humans can follow the exact mapping from data input to prediction. We would have to consider millions of weights that interact in a complex way to understand a prediction by a neural network. To interpret the behavior and predictions of neural networks, we need specific interpretation methods.

A. Explainable Transparent DNN

The researchers [11] in their survey paper and author [4] in his book made a good contribution towards understanding XAI. There are two different pathways towards Explainable Transparent DNN. The first method is post-hoc processing, where ML gives analytic statements, visualizations, and explanations by example. And the second method is transparency design, where developers understand the model structure, understand single components, and understand training algorithms.

B. Understanding the Features

Pixel Attribution (Saliency Maps) methods highlight the pixels relevant for the classification decision for a specific image made by a neural network. Sensitivity analysis [8] (SA) identifies the most relevant input features that are the most sensitive for the output. Layer-wise relevance propagation [9] (LRP) redistributes the prediction backward using local redistribution rules and assigns a relevance score to each input feature. Later introduced, Gradient-based methods are usually faster to compute than model-agnostic methods like LIME and SHAP. However, they are susceptible to noise. SmoothGrad [10] solves that problem by adding by artificial noise. Still, it is difficult to know whether an explanation is correct, and a huge part of the evaluation is only qualitative.

C. Feature Visualization

Convolutional neural networks learn abstract features and concepts from the raw image pixels. Feature Visualization technique visualizes these learned features by activation maximization process. Network Dissection algorithm [1] labels neural network units (e.g., channels) with human concepts. However, in an entangled network, there would be no individual unit for a class, and all channels would contribute to the recognition of that class. For a given input image and a trained network (fixed weights), the algorithm forward propagates the image pixels up to the target layer, upscale the activations

to match the original image size, and compare the maximum activations with the ground truth pixel-wise segmentation. Network Dissection only aligns human concepts with positive activations but not with negative activations of channels. However, we have seen negative activations contribute to correct predictions too.

D. Learning Semantic Graphs

The authors [12] propose a method that learns a graphical model called an explanatory graph to reveal the knowledge hierarchy hidden inside a pre-trained CNN model. However, it works best for a disentangled network. Semantic Graphs create an understandable relation between prediction and different parts of hidden layers. Authors in their later work introduced additional losses to force the CNN to disentangle.

E. Generation of Explanations

The generation of explanations for image-based problems can produce understandable AI. The authors [2] propose a new model through a novel loss function based on sampling and reinforcement learning. The network focuses on the discriminating properties of the visible object to explain the image, predicts a class label, and explains the relevant features of why the predicted class label is appropriate for this image. The authors used the LSTM stack to produce an explanatory text sequence.

F. Algorithm unrolling

Like the previous section, the algorithm unrolling [5] is a technique to build Interpretable, efficient deep learning networks. An iterative algorithm executes a subnetwork and creates an interpretable layer in each step. After completion of the iterative algorithm, the complete network is produced. Algorithm unrolling helps intermediate layers to increase more reliable performance by learning different hyperparameters.

IV. CONCLUSION

The research of problem-solving using DNN and explainable DNN are two different worlds. There are lots of great DNN algorithms used as a black box, and XAI researchers try to apply post-hoc processing to explain the model's prediction and incorporate trustworthiness into the system. We hope both research paradigms will merge and grow to provide the high-performing glass-box DNNs with human-in-the-loop. The researchers and developers will understand the model structure, understand single components, and understand training algorithms. It will create the base for trustworthy explainable deep learning models.

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